

USE OF EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT EDUCATION OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The article describes forms of organizing independent learning for students of secondary schools, as well as effective methods of using electronic educational resources and innovative technologies when performing independent work.*

Keywords: *independent work, independent learning, educational resource, innovative technologies, SMART education, mobility, presentation, methodology, presentation.*

INTRODUCTION

It is important to pay particular attention to the fact that as a result of reforms taking place in the socio-economic, political, spiritual and cultural spheres in our country, it depends on the system of continuous education, which determines the intellectual and creative capabilities of future specialists and is considered the main condition for its development. At the same time, the growth and high development of creative and intellectual potential not only affects the quality and effectiveness of education and the improvement of the system in this area, but also significantly contributes to the development of all areas of this social process.” secret shows. That is why today one of the strategic directions in education, the innovative activity of continuing education institutions is defined as the main factor. At present time, the educational process of traditional forms in the general secondary education system is being replaced by a unique, innovative, innovative education. Creativity and creative thinking develop as a result of the development of independent learning of students using educational resources and the creation of an innovative educational environment.

LITERARY ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

It should be suggested that among local scientists, the works of U.N. Nishonaliev, O.K. Tolipov, A.R. Khojaboev, N. Muslimov, A.O. Koisynov, Sh. Shodiev, K. Davletov, Y. Khaidarov are known. independent work can be noted. They developed and put into practice textbooks and teaching aids for independent education in the system of general secondary education, higher and secondary specialized vocational education.

It is noteworthy that Benjamin Bloom, a professor at the University of Chicago, among foreign scientists, created a taxonomy of educational goals in the field of acquiring knowledge.

Although the literature provides complete information about various aspects of the innovative approach in organizing an independent educational process, the stages of formation and development of innovative processes are not sufficiently covered.

DISCUSSION.

It is necessary to define a clear management and action strategy to ensure the effectiveness of the preparation and activities of students in secondary educational institutions. In increasing the activity and efficiency of students, the stages of independent learning and the use of innovative educational technologies are in any case individual and the following must be taken into account:

□ firstly, in order to implement innovative technologies in the organization of independent education, it is necessary to separately prepare participants in the process of independent education, which requires special attention from teachers of general education institutions involved in these cases, and requires additional efforts. Thanks to this process, each participant develops competence in working with electronic educational resources, and through these educational resources an independent educational process is effectively organized.

□ secondly, organizational and managerial decisions that ensure the competence of independent work and the use of innovative technologies should be made by students in a group, since these are the factors that motivate most of the team of participants to the innovation process in a short time. period of time, reliably and effectively provides, and the decisions made with the group in this process are effective and efficient tools for applying innovative pedagogical methods.

For effectively organizing the independent learning for students and improve the methods of effective use of innovative educational technologies, it is necessary to develop competencies in working with electronic educational resources and implement the following stages of the process of effective organization through these educational resources:

First stage. It will require a conscious understanding by students of general secondary education institutions of the importance and effectiveness of e-learning resources that can be used in the process of independent learning, that is, to develop or improve their future ideas. Many studies show that the initiators of this process are students, and the main organizers of this stage are the joint activities of teachers and students.

Second phase. The introduction of one or another innovation by a group of students organizing an independent educational process consists of improving this process using various electronic educational resources.

Third stage. Formation of practical competence of students in innovative activities and use of educational resources when organizing an independent educational process based on electronic educational resources in an electronic educational environment. What do students gain from such processes? What are these processes for? At this stage, you can get answers to the above and additional questions. This can be achieved if the participants in this process are supported and consciously understood based on their desires and intellectual abilities.

Fourth stage. To organize independent learning, it is necessary to problem-analyze the task of independent work, create a problem area and determine the main aspects of the task in a problem-oriented and solution-oriented state.

Fifth stage. Based on the analysis of the problem situation and task and the results of identifying the main problem, the stages of organizing independent education based on electronic educational resources are developed.

Sixth stage. To implement the problem under study and the process of independent education, it is necessary to determine the exact organization and management process, that is, to develop a plan and program for its implementation.

Seventh stage. To organize independent learning and coordinate the management process in his future career, he will take the first steps to implement the project idea.

The proposed ideas for improving the process of organizing independent learning for students in secondary educational institutions using electronic educational resources are described as follows:

First, it is a process of improving and developing further innovative capabilities of the participating team;

Secondly, the use of e-learning resources that enhance the self-directed learning process ensures effectiveness.

The fourth stage is the main one within the recommended stages of the process of developing competence to work with electronic educational resources and organizing independent learning using these educational resources and is important in determining the main problem of the tasks of independent education. . After all, it is impossible to start innovative activities, that is, activities that solve the problem of tasks performed in the process of independent education, without defining a specific problem.

In the process of independent education, if the analysis of the problem is started and it is carried out correctly, its result is professional activity based on vitality, and this result allows us to direct the solution to existing problems of the educational process.

It should be noted that no student can be forced to participate in this process. Here you can develop competencies for working with electronic educational resources based on the introduction of innovations in the process of independent education, analyzing the problems of existing tasks in organizing independent education, and also improving the methodology for organizing independent education. education using these educational resources we will need.

Competencies for improving the methodology of organizing independent education:

determination of a reform roadmap covering the methodology for organizing independent education;

conducting targeted research based on the “road map”;

analysis of the conducted research and generalization of the results.

Competencies in using the necessary information via the Internet:

independent determination of the necessary information;

be able to independently analyze and evaluate the necessary information;

- search and find sources of information based on the essence of the problem being solved;

- understand the results of the information received.

Competencies for working on electronic educational resources:

systematic use of electronic resources (engineering programs, mobile programs, electronic textbooks, electronic manuals, etc.);

sort the list of Internet resources according to editing rules.

Competencies for working with text information provided through information technology:

determine the topic, plan and list of references;

identifying the main problem, ideas and conclusions of the information presented;

briefly describe the key words that highlight the main essence of the problem being solved;

process and store the information presented, as well as make a broader statement based on ideas about their essence.

At present time, the goal is to introduce “SMART education” at the level of modern requirements in educational institutions. Thus, the introduction of technologies is aimed at informatization of educational and management processes of educational institutions, as well as the basic principles of creating a unified platform for educational institutions that can be used, provide interactive services and be integrated with other information systems.

Table

Ease of organizing an independent educational process through the use of SMART technologies in the educational process.

Comfort for teachers	Comfort for students
<p>An innovative approach to organizing independent education;</p> <p>Convenient exchange of information with students;</p> <p>Formation of a virtual image based on reality;</p> <p>Easy management of the self-paced learning process;</p> <p>Variety of multimedia;</p> <p>Integrated e-learning environment;</p> <p>Possibilities for ensuring the integration of the educational process and innovative technologies in an integrated e-learning environment;</p> <p>Opportunities to easily and simply determine the abilities of students depending on their needs and level in this process;</p> <p>Availability of opportunities to establish cooperation and exchange of information with several educational institutions;</p> <p>Increasing the intensity and effectiveness of training.</p>	<p>A large number of sources of information;</p> <p>Availability of technological capabilities;</p> <p>Providing various educational interactive services;</p> <p>Mobility of education (presence of information exchange process);</p> <p>A large number of software tools that provide the ability to implement creative and research projects;</p> <p>Availability of opportunities to exchange information with the teacher and other students;</p> <p>Development of creative abilities and opportunities for independent implementation of these skills;</p> <p>The ability to obtain the necessary information regardless of place and time;</p> <p>Availability of opportunities to prepare for these processes in any case.</p>

SMART is the automation and management of the educational process, providing mobility in order to implement education in practice, in order to ensure use by users in any accessible area, at a convenient time, via the Internet.

SMART – education is essentially a new educational environment; is to combine the capabilities of the teacher and students to use global knowledge and move from passive content to active content, that is, educational activity.

SMART group software. Different E-learning resources are used to organize such groups. For example, in the process of organizing self-study, the iSpring program is used to prepare presentations. Typically, when preparing a presentation, Microsoft Power Point software is used in most cases. But such presentations can only be in the format of this product (ppt, pptx). Today, as a result of the development of innovative technologies and the advent of distance education, presentation files can be viewed directly on the Internet in flash (swf) format or based on HTML 5 technology. iSpring Free, iSpring PRO and iSpring Presenter are among the programs that allow you to create flash videos from presentations created in Microsoft Power Point.

CONCLUSION.

By summarizing, it should be noted that ensuring the integration of education is an important criterion for the development of the field. One of the main tasks facing the education system today is to teach students to constantly develop the skills and competencies of independent

work and to form a perfect personality. Therefore, today in the educational process, an important process is the theoretical and practical study of the methodology for implementing results, based on the connection between the innovative socio-economic sphere and the integrated educational environment.

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